

IKMLab@BC8 Track 3: Sequence Tagging for Position-Aware Human Phenotype Extraction with Pre-trained Language Models

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Abstract

Automatic extraction and normalization of human phenotypes from unstructured physical examination reports is a crucial and challenging task in clinical genetics. This paper presents the system submitted by IKMLab for the BioCreative VIII Task 3 - Genetic Phenotype Extraction and Normalization. We target Subtask 3b and aim at providing accurate locations of human phenotype findings given an observation text. Our system consists of two stages. In the first stage, we use the output of an existing baseline (e.g., PhenoTagger) to obtain a preliminary set of Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) terms for each observation. Then, in the second stage, we design a sequence tagging schema based on a pre-trained language model and perform token classification to locate spans for the HPO terms. Our best system achieved 60.4% and 64.2% in Exact and Overlapping F1 scores during the final evaluations. In addition, further experiments show that our approach helps to better locate separated and consecutive spans describing HPO terms from observations.

Introduction

The automatic extraction of human phenotypes from unstructured text helps physicians and researchers swiftly identify positive findings or potential diseases. However, ambiguities or abbreviations describing specific features are common in medical report descriptions. Therefore, a normalization step is required to map textual spans of findings to the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) (1) to ensure accurate recognition. BioCreative VIII Task 3 provides a dataset derived from the observations of the dysmorphology physical examination. Participants in this task are tasked with creating a system to extract and normalize the key findings in the observations based on the HPO. For example, given a text observation: “*EYES: long palpebral fissures with slight downslant. Normal eyebrows.*”, a system must return one of the following types of answers: (i) all recognized HPO term IDs from the observation; (ii) the span positions corresponding to the extracted HPO term IDs. Subtask 3a evaluates the former response type, while Subtask 3b assesses the latter. Additionally, the dataset also comprises normal observations. Hence, a submitted system must identify the state of each observation and bypass the normal ones, making Task 3 more challenging.

Our Approach

Motivation and System Overview

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed system for BioCreative VIII Task 3. (a) Training (b) Inference.

A direct approach to Task 3 would involve leveraging existing phenotype recognition methods, such as PhenoTagger (2) or PhenoBERT (3). However, a limitation emerges: they can identify only consecutive spans of HPO terms. This is because a text segmentation step is involved in both PhenoTagger and PhenoBERT for splitting input text into n-gram sentences. Notably, in the training and validation sets, **14.4%** and **14.0%** of HPO terms, respectively, are annotated as separated spans. This implies that methods like PhenoTagger and PhenoBERT might fail to locate these HPO terms. Our work, therefore, is concentrated on Subtask 3b, with the primary goal of handling of separated spans for HPO terms. To create a system for accurately locating text relevant to HPO terms from an observation, we built a sequence tagging framework on top of the output of a base phenotype recognition model, such as PhenoTagger (2). The system is shown in Figure 1. In the next sections, we describe our pre-preprocessing, training, and inference approaches.

Pre-processing

We use NLTK’s `word_tokenize` function to tokenize the observations in the provided dataset. Next, each token in an observation is labeled for sequence tagging. Here we employ a ternary tagging schema: “1” for positive findings, “2” for normal findings, and “0” for other tokens. Then we map the labels to each token according to the spans annotated by the task organizers¹. Since NLTK treats punctuation as separate tokens, we assign labels to them, as illustrated in Figure 1 (a).

¹ We found some span ranges that miss one character, so we corrected them (Train: 11 rows, Val: 1 row) manually.

Training

Observations are often annotated with multiple HPO terms by the organizers, as we denote “HPO_ID_1, ..., HPO_ID_N” to indicate that N HPO terms have been labeled for an observation in Figure 1 (a). To enable sequence tagging training, we leverage the HPO dictionary (‘HP2Terms.tsv’) provided by the organizers. We then append the associated HPO text (also tokenized by NLTK) to the observation, with an insertion of the [SEP] token to separate the two types of text. The appended HPO text is labeled as “1”, which is also shown in Figure 1 (a). Note that we intend to create a paradox in the sequence labels for the normal cases, as in the second example of Figure 1 (a), since the text listed in the HPO dictionary represents terms for positive findings. For implementation, we use HuggingFace Transformers in PyTorch and fine-tune BERT for sequence tagging. We tested our approach with PubMedBERT (4), BioLinkBERT (5), and Bioformer (6), and reported the best model based on F1-score from the validation set. All experiments were performed on a single RTX 2080 Ti GPU.

Inference

Our inference process is illustrated in Figure 1 (b). To obtain the predictions for Task 3, we structure three main steps in our pipeline. In the first step, which we call “HPO Identification” in Figure 3 (b), we employ base models, such as PhenoTagger (2) or PhenoBERT (3), to generate a preliminary prediction set of HPO terms from the observations in the evaluation set. The hyperparameters we use for PhenoTagger and PhenoBERT are the same as the default settings. Next, we perform span localization based on the preliminary prediction set. We also append each HPO term of the preliminary prediction set to an observation with a [SEP] token. Then, we use our trained sequence tagging model to predict the labels of the input tokens. In the final step, which we call “Token Aggregation” in Figure 3 (b), we aggregate the subword tokens from the BERT output and obtain the HPO positions corresponding to the tokens predicted as “1”. Before obtaining the final predictions, we screen out the HPO terms predicted as “2” by our sequence tagging model. This step provides an opportunity to refine the preliminary predictions from the base model and avoid misclassification for the normal cases.

Results and Discussion

In Table 1, we present the results of Task 3 for our proposed method in comparison to the baseline models: PhenoTagger and PhenoBERT, using the validation set. Our focus is primarily on Subtask 3b. Since our approach is built on top of the base models, our aim was to measure the improvement our method brings to these models. We observe improvements in exact span localization (ExactExt) for both base models through our method, in particular a greater boost over PhenoBERT. Additionally, integrating predictions from both base models (Union²) led to an even higher score. Consequently, we selected the configurations from the last two rows in Table 1 for the final evaluation, where the results are present in Table 2. Interestingly, the system utilizing the BioLinkBERT-large model underperformed compared to its BioLinkBERT-base counterpart. We hypothesize that the large model might have suffered from overfitting.

² Predictions from PhenoTagger are retained when an overlapping occurs for the predicted spans.

Considering our results are intrinsically tied to the base models' performance, we explored our method's potential when with an accurate predicted HPO set during the initial phase. Clearly, as seen in the last row of Table 1, our method can more accurately localize the HPO spans, given the correct HPO terms. Further analysis was conducted to assess the enhancement in performance for both separated and consecutive spans on the validation set. Figure 2 shows that the results on the observations with both types of tokens can be improved through the proposed method.

Conclusion

We propose a sequence tagging framework designed to improve the performance of span localization for specific human phenotypes in observation text. Our technique shows potential promise in localizing HPO-relevant spans given an observation text and an initial prediction set of HPO terms. Future studies in HPO extraction and normalization can use our method to enhance the localization capability of HPO spans on top of their approaches.

Table 1: Evaluations on the validation set. Scores are shown as F1 / Precision / Recall.

Base Model	Our Method	Evaluation Type		
		NormOnly	ExactExt	OverExt
PhenoTagger	-	66.6 / 63.5 / 70.0	60.7 / 60.3 / 61.1	66.5 / 63.5 / 70.0
PhenoTagger	BioLinkBERT-base	66.6 / 69.7 / 63.8	62.7 / 67.8 / 58.3	66.4 / 69.6 / 63.4
PhenoBERT	-	65.5 / 74.5 / 53.9	50.4 / 68.4 / 40.0	62.4 / 74.4 / 53.7
PhenoBERT	BioLinkBERT-base	63.3 / 80.5 / 52.2	60.1 / 79.2 / 48.4	63.1 / 80.4 / 51.9
Union*	BioLinkBERT-base	66.8 / 67.5 / 66.1	63.1 / 65.7 / 60.8	66.6 / 67.4 / 65.7
Union*	BioLinkBERT-large	66.8 / 67.7 / 65.9	63.6 / 66.1 / 61.2	66.6 / 67.6 / 65.6
Gold	BioLinkBERT-base	96.9 / 99.8 / 94.2	88.7 / 99.8 / 79.9	96.6 / 99.8 / 93.6

*Union stands for using union predictions of HPO sets from PhenoTagger and PhenoBERT. "-" indicates using the base model alone.

Table 2: Final evaluation scores in F1 / Precision / Recall.

Base Model	Our Method	Evaluation Type		
		NormOnly	ExactExt	OverExt
Union*	BioLinkBERT-base	64.4 / 76.2 / 55.7	60.4 / 74.5 / 50.8	64.2 / 76.1 / 55.6
Union*	BioLinkBERT-large	64.1 / 75.9 / 55.5	60.2 / 74.2 / 50.6	63.7 / 75.7 / 55.0

*Union stands for using union predictions of HPO sets from PhenoTagger and PhenoBERT.

Figure 2: Improvements over the separated and the consecutive spans on the validation set. "Ours" indicates using the BioLinkBERT-base model fine-tuned for sequence tagging.

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